

Benefits of increasing reforecast ensemble size

C3S2_370_MF – Operational production of seasonal forecasts

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2. Executive summary

The operational Météo-France System 8 used for seasonal forecast provision in the C3S2_370_MF contract features different ensemble sizes between real-time forecasts (51 members) and reforecasts (25 members). This raises the question whether the verification metrics of Météo-France System 8 computed with the 25-member reforecast are relevant to document the performance of the system in real-time. Météo-France has investigated this question in WP4/Task 4.2 of the C3S2_370_MF contract, entitled “Influence of the ensemble size on user-oriented products”, for which this report is the final deliverable. This work builds on additional reforecast members computed in WP1/Task 1.3 of the same contract (described in Deliverable D370.1.3.1).

Based on verification for European climate (seasonal near-surface temperature and precipitation) and the associated atmospheric modes of variability (North Atlantic Oscillation, East Atlantic mode, Scandinavian Blocking), the overall conclusion is that the differences between verification metrics computed from 25 and 51 members are limited. More precisely, drawing 25 members leads to expected scores that are already close to the 51-member values. Due to these modest benefits, matching reforecast and real-time ensemble size is not a high priority for the next Météo-France seasonal forecasting system, but could be implemented if affordable to ensure a better consistency between both datasets.

3. Introduction

The current Météo-France seasonal forecasting system (System 8, [Météo-France, 2021](#)) operated for the C3S2_370_MF contract produces real-time ensemble forecasts on a monthly basis. These real-time forecasts come along with a set of reforecasts initialized with past initial conditions across the 1993-2016 period. The main role of reforecasts is to provide a robust sample to: (i) estimate the climatology of the seasonal forecasting system (ii) train calibration or bias-correction schemes (iii) assess the expected performances of the forecasts with verification methods. However, in Météo-France System 8, one major difference between the official real-time forecasts and the official reforecasts is the ensemble size: 51 members for real-time versus 25 members for the reforecasts.

This discrepancy in ensemble size raises questions about the validity of any conclusion drawn from the analysis of the reforecast. Is it indeed possible to extrapolate the behaviour of a 25-member reforecast to the real-time forecasts? And should the next seasonal forecasting system rely on an equal ensemble size between reforecast and real-time? In order to investigate this issue, Météo-France computed 26 additional ensemble members in the reforecasts for experimental purposes, so that the ensemble size matches that of the real-time (51). This extended reforecast was made within Task 1.3 of the present C3S contract and will be used to address several scientific questions in this deliverable.

The documentation of Météo-France system 8 includes a wide variety of verification metrics that were computed using the official 25-member reforecast¹. In the meantime, it has often

1 <http://seasonal.meteo.fr/content/PS-scores?language=en>

been shown that forecast scores are supposed to increase with ensemble size up to a certain point (e.g. [Déqué 1997](#)), which suggests that the 25-member reforecast might be underestimating the real-time forecast performance. In this deliverable, we investigate whether the official 25-member evaluations are still valid for 51 members by using the reforecast extension. The verification focus is set on seasonal mean forecasts of climate parameters (near-surface temperature, precipitation) over Europe, and modes of atmospheric circulation variability that are relevant for the European domain (North Atlantic Oscillation, East Atlantic mode, Scandinavian Blocking). After presenting the data and methodology (Section 3), we address the following questions:

- Are the official 25-member reforecast scores representative of the 51-member real-time performance? (Section 4)
- What is the optimal reforecast ensemble size for verification? (Section 5)

Besides these core questions, the extended reforecast provides a benchmark for verification of 51-member forecasts, to which alternative forecasting strategies can be compared: this is the point of Section 6. Finally, Section 7 summarizes the main conclusions of the deliverable and provides a recommendation on reforecast ensemble size for the next Météo-France seasonal forecasting system.

4. Data and methodology

3.1. Reforecast data

Météo-France System 8 is based on the CNRM-CM coupled climate model ([Voldoire et al. 2019](#)) and its output data is stored on a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid with 180 latitudes and 360 longitudes, starting at 89.5°S and 0.5°W and extending northwards and eastwards. The official reforecasts consist in 25 ensemble members for each initialization month over the 1993-2016 years, and provide a numerical integration up to 7-month lead time. The ensemble members are generated through stochastic perturbations of the atmosphere as described in [Batté and Déqué \(2016\)](#).

Moreover, although each initialization date is referred to as the 1st of each month (e.g. 1 February 2006), the ensemble is made up of members that were actually initialized with initial conditions from three different dates: one member uses the initial conditions on the 1st of the month (e.g. 1 member starting 1 February 2006) while two groups of 12 members are initialized respectively on the prior and second prior Thursdays before the 1st (e.g. 12 members starting 20 January 2006 and 12 members starting 27 January 2006).

This three-tier initialization procedure is the same as that of the 51-member real-time forecast, except that 12 members are initialized on each previous Thursday instead of 25. To mirror the real-time setup, the experimental reforecast extension consisted in running another 13 members initialized on the same two Thursdays as the official reforecasts, thus reaching a full ensemble size of 51.

The reforecast extension was completed for the February, May, August and November initializations. This enables to sample the annual cycle by targeting the usual meteorological seasons at 1-month lead-time: spring for March-April-May (MAM), summer for June-July-

August (JJA), autumn for September-October-November (SON) and winter for December-January-February (DJF) respectively.

3.2. Verification focus and reference data

Verification of the 51-member reforecast has been carried out so as to follow exactly the same procedure as implemented for the official 25-member reforecast verification displayed at <http://seasonal.meteo.fr/content/PS-scores?language=en>. Results will mostly be shown for the 1-month lead season (e.g MAM 2006 for the February 2006 initialization), referred to as LT1, for each initialization month of the extension. Scores are computed over 1993-2016.

The climate variables under consideration for verification are near-surface temperature (T2M) and total precipitation (RR) in all grid points in a box encompassing Europe (EU, 29.5°W-49.5°E; 30.5°N-70.5°N). Note that investigation has also been carried out on other boxes such as Northeast Brazil (BRNE, 49.5°W-35.5°W; 17.5°S-0.5°S) and Indonesia (INDO, 95.5°E-144.5°E; 9.5°S-4.5°N) for comparison, but will not be shown extensively. T2M reference data is extracted at 1° resolution from the ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al, 2020), while the RR reference data comes from the GPCP rainfall product (Adler et al, 2003) at 2.5° resolution. Finally, in agreement with the verification procedure on the official Météo-France seasonal forecast website mentioned above, these climate variables are verified after box averaging, with removal of sea grid points for T2M and without removal for RR. The reason for removing sea grid points in T2M is that they would drastically increase forecast skill relative to land grid points, while being irrelevant for most users.

Verification has also been carried out on indices representing modes of variability at the seasonal scale. These modes are the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), the East Atlantic mode (EA) and the Scandinavian Blocking (SCAN), representing various patterns of atmospheric circulation in the Euro-Atlantic region that significantly influence the European climate at a seasonal scale. They are already routinely issued by Météo-France for its seasonal forecast bulletin and are computed in the reforecast extension following the same procedure. For each member, the reforecast 500 hPa geopotential (Z500) anomaly field for the full season (e.g MAM 2006) is projected on three predefined patterns corresponding to each mode. A similar operation is applied to the reference Z500 anomaly from ERA5 for verification. The predefined patterns were themselves determined from the historical ERA5 data with Rotated Principal Components Analysis (Barnston and Livezey, 1987). The reader is invited to refer to the official documentation ([Météo-France/DCSC/AVH, 2017a](#)) for more details.

3.3. Verification metrics

As described above, the verified data corresponds to a box-averaged T2M index, a box-averaged RR index, the NAO index, the EA index and the SCAN index. For each index and each initialization, there is a sample of 24 years (1993-2016) to verify the ensemble reforecast against the corresponding reference. The verification metrics to be shown in this deliverable are the time correlation (CORR) and the area under the ROC curve for a probabilistic forecast of a value above the higher climatological tercile (ROCA HT). Note that these scores were chosen among the various metrics provided in the official verification of Météo-France system 8. Others have also been computed but will not be shown for the sake of brevity, such as

the area under the ROC curve for the lower tercile (ROCA LT), or the Ranked Probability Skill Score (RPSS).

3.4. Reforecast resampling

The extended reforecast comprises 51 members. In this deliverable, it will mostly be regarded as a benchmark since it has as many members as the real-time forecasts. Among those 51 members, the first 25 correspond to the official reforecast and their scores will be confronted to those of the full 51-member benchmark. However, we need to account for the fact that those first 25 members only represent one reforecast possibility and that a different set of 25 members might lead to different results.

These differences can be assessed with a bootstrap procedure where 25 members are randomly drawn out of 51, without replacement. The operation is repeated 1,000 times so as to sample the distributions of the reforecast scores. In this context, the official 25-member reforecast scores can be seen as one specific draw from these distributions. This bootstrap approach enables to estimate the uncertainty in verification metrics that arises from the choice of perturbations used to generate the members. Note that this bootstrap procedure is also used for other reforecast ensemble sizes, e.g drawing 5, 10, 20, 30 or 40 members out of 51.

5. Are the official reforecast scores representative of the real-time forecast performance?

In this section, the 51-member reforecast is considered as a benchmark. The main purpose is to quantify how much the verification metrics from a 25-member reforecast differ from those computed with this benchmark.

4.1. How close are the performances of the 25 and 51-member reforecasts?

4.1.1. Comparison of reforecast climatologies

Although it does not correspond to a verification metric, a comparison between the 25 and 51-member reforecast climatologies is a relevant starting point to evaluate the impact of ensemble size. As mentioned in the introduction, estimating the climatology of the forecasting system is one of the main roles of a reforecast. In addition, the climatology distribution from the reforecast is often used in post-processing of real-time forecasts, such as simple bias correction (i.e subtraction of the climatological mean).

Figure 1 shows the reforecast climatology of EU-averaged T2M, EU-averaged RR and NAO index in December-January-February when the forecasting system is initialized in November (lead time 1). While the red curves correspond to the benchmark climatology distributions inferred from the 51-member reforecast, the blue ones show the distributions available in the official reforecast. It is clear that the differences between the two climatologies are very small, and the results are similar for other quantities and/or initialization months (not shown).

In other words, the climatology of Météo-France system 8 can be indifferently sampled from 51 or 25 members. A direct consequence is that 25 members are already enough for bias correction.

Figure 1: Reforecast climatology distributions of Météo-France system 8 in DJF at lead time 1 in the official reforecast (blue) and extended reforecast (red), for EU-averaged T2M (above), EU-averaged RR (middle) and NAO index (below). The sample sizes are 24 years x 25 members for the blue curve and 24 years x 51 member for the red curves.

4.1.2. Net differences in verification metrics

Figure 2 proposes a synthesis visualisation of the net differences between verification metrics in the official 25-member reforecast and the extended 51-member reforecast. For the sake of brevity, the results are only shown for correlation of T2M and RR in EU box, as well as correlation and ROC area for the higher tercile for NAO. Each table features the four initializations (February, May, August, November) in columns and the lead time in rows from 0 to 4 (e.g FMA, MAM... up to JJA for February initialization). The net differences appear on the bottom row while the benchmark 51-member reforecast scores are provided on the top row.

The main conclusion from Figure 2 is that the net difference is often very small (e.g less than 0.1 unit of score) or equal to zero. This is particularly true for the first lead times which are the main focus of seasonal forecasting. Also note that it still holds true for other scores not shown here. Moreover, the sign of the difference is highly variable depending on the lead time, initialization date, parameter or verification metric: there is no indication of a systematic underestimation of the 51-member scores by the 25-member reforecast. These first results suggest there is no need to increase the reforecast ensemble size larger than 25 members for verification of Météo-France system 8. In the following subsections, we dig further into these results by estimating the uncertainty of 25-member scores and the dependency to climate variability and lead time.

Figure 2: (Top) Synthesis tables of various scores of the extended 51-member reforecast (benchmark) at lead times 0 to 4 months in the February, May, August and November initializations. (Bottom) Synthesis tables of the differences between the same scores computed from 25 members minus 51 members. (First column) Correlation of EU-averaged T2M (Second column) Correlation of EU-averaged RR (Third column) Correlation of NAO index (Fourth column) ROC area for the Higher Tercile of NAO index.

4.2. How do seasonal variations of scores change with ensemble size?

The top row in Figure 2 shows a large variability of scores across the four initializations. For instance, correlation for EU-averaged precipitation at lead time 1 is higher for the February and August starts (~ 0.4-0.5) than for the May and November starts (~ 0-0.2). This suggests a seasonal cycle in the forecasting system performance. The question that arises is the robustness of such seasonal variations when less than 51 members are used to sample the reforecast.

Figure 3 compares the seasonal variations of several verification metrics in the benchmark 51-member reforecasts (blue crosses) and the official 25-member reforecasts (red crosses) at lead time 1-month. The chosen examples are correlation and ROCA HT for T2M over Europe, RR over Europe, NAO and SCAN, but the results are similar for other metrics. They are shown alongside boxplots illustrating the mean, the interquartile range and the 95% confidence interval for a 25-member reforecast, based on 1,000 random draws of 25 members (see Section 3.4). The distributions represented by the boxplots summarize the uncertainty related to member sampling, and therefore to member perturbations.

A preliminary and expected lesson from Figure 3 is that the confidence intervals can be quite large, between 0.1 and 0.2 unit of score, exhibiting uncertainty in the individual verification metrics computed from 25 members. Moreover, this uncertainty appears to be larger for modes of variability (NAO, SCAN) than for surface climate parameters (T2M, RR). The most likely reason for this is the fact that T2M and RR correspond to box-averaged values that smooth the smaller-scale discrepancies among members, while modes of variability are single indices coming from projected fields and are thus more sensitive to member sampling.

In this context of uncertainty in the verification metrics, the official 25-member score is equivalent to one random draw and can sometimes be at the tails of the distribution (e.g. ROCA HT for RR in DJF, correlation for SCAN in DJF). On the contrary, the mean of the 1,000 draws is representative of an intrinsic property of the forecasting system, i.e. the expected score when a 25-member reforecast is produced. Therefore, the mean scores (middle black lines) are generally closer to the reference 51-member reforecast (blue crosses) than the official scores (red crosses).

In order to quantify the agreement in seasonal variations between the 25 and 51-member reforecast (blue vs red), the root mean square difference across the four initialization months (RMSD) is indicated in a corner of each plot. We choose an arbitrary difference threshold of 0.1 point of correlation to consider that the seasonal variations are similar. To be consistent, the equivalent arbitrary threshold for ROCA HT is chosen as 0.05 because a difference between areas under a ROC curve is homogeneous to half of a difference between correlations. This can be understood by considering the work of [Mason and Weigel \(2009\)](#) where a generalization of the area under the ROC curve, noted p_{2AFC} , is proposed using the following relationship with Kendall's correlation coefficient τ :

$$p_{2AFC} = (\tau + 1)/2$$

We notice that the seasonal variation differences are below those thresholds for T2M and RR, and above for NAO and SCAN. This is in agreement with the above-mentioned larger uncertainty in scores for modes of variability as single projection indices (vs box-averaged quantities for T2M and RR).

Because such differences are only valid for the official reforecast as one specific draw of 25 members, Tables 1 and 2 provide information about how these seasonal cycle differences between 25 and 51 members are distributed across the 1,000 random draws (Table 1 for CORR and Table 2 for ROCA HT respectively). Also note that Tables 1 and 2 display results for a larger set of parameters than Figure 3, for which the corresponding figures are shown in Appendix (Figure A1). These additional parameters include T2M and RR averaged over two other geographical boxes: Indonesia (INDO) and Northeast Brazil (BRNE).

Table 1 shows that choosing 25 members instead of 51 should lead to a difference across the seasonal cycle (RMSD) that is mostly less than 0.1 unit of correlation, as shown by the median. The only exception is SCAN, for which the median is slightly above. Moreover, judging by the 95th percentiles, the difference should not exceed 0.2 even in case of an unfavourable draw. More generally, Table 1 is consistent with Figure 3 left column in showing that the correlation discrepancies between 25 and 51 members are larger for modes of variability than for box-averaged surface parameters. Finally, although the main focus of this deliverable is on European climate, an additional comparison can be made with tropical regions INDO and BRNE, where the differences in the seasonal cycle of scores are smaller than over EU, especially for T2M. This is not surprising given that climate is more predictable at the seasonal scale in the Tropics than in mid-latitudes, also leading to a smaller ensemble spread and therefore less sensitivity to member sampling.

Figure 3: Verification metrics of the 51 (blue) and 25-member (red) reforecasts at lead time 1-month in the February, May, August and November initializations, with the means, interquartile range and 95% confidence intervals from 1,000 random draws of 25 members out of 51 (black). The root mean square difference across the four initializations (RMSD) between the values in blue and red is indicated in a corner of each plot.

A comparison between Table 1 and Table 2 shows that the results are similar between correlation and area under the ROC curve, after dividing the thresholds by 2 (e.g. 0.05 unit of area instead of 0.1 point of correlation). The only notable difference is for NAO, which exhibits more prominent seasonal cycle differences between 25 and 51 members in ROCA HT than in correlation.

The conclusion from Tables 1 and 2 is that drawing a 25-member reforecast should be considered enough to capture the seasonal variations of scores that appear with 51 members. It might seem paradoxical when considering the large uncertainties on individual verification metrics as in Figure 3, but there is actually no contradiction: although one single verification metric can range in a large interval depending on the 25-member pick, it is extremely unlikely that one specific pick will have several verification metrics that deviate simultaneously and strongly from the 51-member benchmark.

Variable	Box (if any)	Verification metric	RMSD 25-member (official reforecast)	RMSD median (1,000 draws)	RMSD 95 th percentile (1,000 draws)
T2M	EU	CORR	0.013	0.037	0.063
RR	EU	CORR	0.031	0.041	0.069
T2M	INDO	CORR	0.005	0.004	0.006
RR	INDO	CORR	0.015	0.012	0.029
T2M	BRNE	CORR	0.015	0.009	0.018
RR	BRNE	CORR	0.018	0.023	0.044
NAO		CORR	0.064	0.077	0.140
EA		CORR	0.061	0.043	0.074
SCAN		CORR	0.110	0.104	0.182

Table 1: Root mean square difference of correlation between the 1,000 random draws of 25-member reforecasts against the benchmark 51-member reforecast. Differences are computed across the four initializations (February, May, August, November) at lead time 1-month to quantify the discrepancy in seasonal variations. In purple, differences less than 0.02 indicating a strong agreement. In red, differences greater than 0.1.

Variable	Box (if any)	Verification metric	RMSD 25-member (official reforecast)	RMSD median (1,000 draws)	RMSD 95 th percentile (1,000 draws)
T2M	EU	ROCA HT	0.010	0.020	0.032
RR	EU	ROCA HT	0.014	0.012	0.018
T2M	INDO	ROCA HT	0.005	0.005	0.008
RR	INDO	ROCA HT	0.011	0.009	0.013
T2M	BRNE	ROCA HT	0.009	0.007	0.012
RR	BRNE	ROCA HT	0.004	0.013	0.022
NAO		ROCA HT	0.077	0.069	0.110
EA		ROCA HT	0.035	0.039	0.069
SCAN		ROCA HT	0.056	0.071	0.119

Table 2: Same as Table 1 for ROCA HT. In purple, differences less than 0.01 indicating a strong agreement. In red, differences greater than 0.05.

4.3. How do lead-time variations of scores change with ensemble size?

Similar to Figure 3, Figure 4 illustrates the variations of several verification metrics with lead time. Because such a display requires to set the initialization month, only November is shown for the sake of brevity, with T2M and RR over Europe, NAO and SCAN. Likewise, Figure 4 indicates the root mean square differences (RMSD) between the blue (reference 51 members) and red (official 25 members) values over the five lead times. More details on the distributions of these root mean square differences are given in Tables 3 and 4 for CORR and ROCA HT respectively, while the counterparts of Figure 4 for the additional metrics can be found in Appendix (Figure A2).

The messages from Figure 4 and Tables 2 and 3 broadly remain the same as for seasonal variations. First, there is stronger agreement between 25 and 51 members for box-averaged variables (T2M, RR) than for modes of variability. For T2M, there is also less sensitivity to ensemble size in the tropical areas (INDO, BRNE) than in Europe. Finally, whatever the set of 25 members chosen as a reforecast, the expected difference across lead times compared to the benchmark 51-member reforecast is mostly less than 0.1 unit of correlation or 0.05 unit of area under the ROC curve. 25 members can therefore be considered to provide a sufficient estimate of how verification metrics evolve with lead time, and increasing the reforecast size will not change the overall results.

Figure 4: Verification metrics of the 51 (blue) and 25-member (red) reforecasts at lead times 0 to 4-month in the November initialization, with the means, interquartile range and 95% confidence intervals from 1,000 random draws of 25 members out of 51 (black). The root mean square difference across the five lead times (RMSD) between the values in blue and red is indicated in a corner of each plot.

Variable	Box (if any)	Verification metric (initialization)	RMSD 25-member (official reforecast)	RMSD median (1,000 draws)	RMSD 95 th percentile (1,000 draws)
T2M	EU	CORR (Nov)	0.023	0.046	0.085
RR	EU	CORR (Nov)	0.044	0.050	0.090
T2M	INDO	CORR (Nov)	0.003	0.003	0.007
RR	INDO	CORR (Nov)	0.016	0.024	0.052
T2M	BRNE	CORR (Nov)	0.004	0.008	0.015
RR	BRNE	CORR (Nov)	0.026	0.028	0.057
NAO		CORR (Nov)	0.060	0.082	0.146
EA		CORR (Nov)	0.066	0.052	0.094
SCAN		CORR (Nov)	0.067	0.085	0.160

Table 3: Root mean square difference of correlation between the 25-member reforecast and the reference 51-member reforecast. Differences are computed across the five lead times (LT0 to LT4) for the November initialization to quantify the discrepancy in variations with lead time. In purple, differences less than 0.02 indicating a strong agreement. In red, differences greater than 0.1.

Variable	Box (if any)	Verification metric (initialization)	RMSD 25-member (official reforecast)	RMSD median (1,000 draws)	RMSD 95 th percentile (1,000 draws)
T2M	EU	ROCA HT (Nov)	0.013	0.021	0.037
RR	EU	ROCA HT (Nov)	0.013	0.011	0.019
T2M	INDO	ROCA HT (Nov)	0.005	0.004	0.008
RR	INDO	ROCA HT (Nov)	0.011	0.008	0.014
T2M	BRNE	ROCA HT (Nov)	0.006	0.006	0.012
RR	BRNE	ROCA HT (Nov)	0.010	0.016	0.032
NAO		ROCA HT (Nov)	0.040	0.067	0.114
EA		ROCA HT (Nov)	0.051	0.049	0.081
SCAN		ROCA HT (Nov)	0.070	0.075	0.122

Table 4: Same as Table 3 for ROCA HT. In purple, differences less than 0.01 indicating a strong agreement. In red, differences greater than 0.05.

4.4. Does ensemble size affect the impact of climate trend?

The official Météo-France system 8 scores also include correlations computed after removing a linear trend across the 24 years of reforecast. The idea is to assess whether the forecasting system has skill in predicting interannual climate variability beyond climate change which is implicitly included in the provided forcings and initial conditions. As a result, the correlation after linear detrending is expected to be lower than the correlation without detrending for variables that exhibit a strong trend, starting with near-surface temperature.

Figure 5 shows the differences between non-detrended and detrended correlations at lead-time 1 month for EU-averaged T2M. As in Figures 3 and 4, the results are shown for the 51-member reforecast, the official 25-member reforecast, and the 1,000 random draws. The non-detrended correlation is indeed larger than the detrended correlation for most target seasons (positive differences), but there are seasonal variations in agreement with literature (e.g the impact of trend on European temperature is larger in summer than in winter, [Rigal et al. 2019](#)).

Regarding the role of reforecast size, the conclusion is similar to the previous sections: the impact on correlation difference is small, suggesting that forecast performance is influenced by the climate trend irrespective of the ensemble size.

Figure 5: Differences between the non-detrended minus detrended correlations of EU-averaged T2M in the 51 (blue) and 25-member (red) reforecasts at lead time 1-month in the February, May, August and November initializations, with the means, interquartile range and 95% confidence intervals from 1,000 random draws of 25 members out of 51.

4.5. Conclusion: Is the official reforecast representative of the real-time forecast performance?

Judging by the previous analyses, undersampling the distribution of the 51-member forecasts over a past period by running a 25-member reforecast is sufficient to provide an overview of the variations in verification metrics as illustrated in synthesis tables like Figure 2 top row. This can be explained by the proximity between the benchmark 51-member scores and the expected scores when 25 members are randomly selected. In this respect, the official 25-member reforecast scores can be regarded as representative of the performance of the real-time forecasting system. Conversely, no important and systematic change in scores should be expected when increasing the reforecast ensemble size beyond 25 members.

However, there is a caveat in using only 25 members, if the user interest lies in one specific score at fixed initialization and lead time (e.g NAO correlation in DJF at lead time 1-month). In some cases when the uncertainty related to member sampling is large, there is always a risk that the score estimate from a 25-member reforecast greatly differs from the benchmark value (e.g by more than 0.1 point of correlation). In those cases, it would be recommended not to give too much credit to the numerical value of the score itself, depending on the user's needs. This robustness issue is discussed in the next section.

6. What is the optimal reforecast ensemble size for verification?

The optimal ensemble size refers to the trade-off between computational cost and the benefits of having more members. This is a two-tier question, referring both to: (i) the optimal ensemble size to maximize reforecast performance (ii) the optimal ensemble size to ensure a robust forecast verification relative to changes in member sampling

To investigate those points, Figure 6 illustrates the evolution of some verification metrics with the ensemble size. The score estimates are taken as the mean over 1,000 random draws out of the pool of 51 members, along with their 95% confidence interval. Regarding the maximization of forecast performance (point i), the focus is on the ensemble size when the mean value reaches saturation. Regarding point (ii), the focus is on the evolution of the confidence interval with ensemble size. More precisely, a maximum confidence interval width of 0.1 is arbitrarily chosen as the threshold for robustness of correlation and a similar threshold of 0.05 is chosen for robustness of area under the ROC curve. Should specific robustness requirements be specified by a user, those thresholds could be adjusted but the comparison across verification metrics would remain qualitatively the same. Figure 6 is completed by Tables 5 and 6, which summarize those points for a larger set of indices for CORR and ROCA HT respectively. The counterparts of Figure 6 for the additional metrics are provided in Appendix (Figure A3).

The main results from Figure 6 and Tables 5 and 6 are the following:

- 1) At 25 members, the expected values of the verification metrics are already close to saturation. They can be deemed representative of the infinite ensemble size performance.
- 2) The verification metrics for sensible climate (T2M, RR) are more robust than for modes of variability. They need fewer members to reach the same confidence interval width.

3) Assuming a confidence interval width of 0.1 (correlation) or 0.05 (area under ROC curve) as the maximum threshold for robustness to changes in member sampling, some verification metrics cannot be considered robust even at 45 members, especially for modes of variability.

As a complement to the caveat raised in Section 4.5, this last result #3 suggests that 51 members could actually be as insufficient as 25 for robust estimates of forecast skill. In other words, giving a definite answer to the minimum ensemble size for robust scores is beyond the scope of this deliverable as it would require a pool of members that is larger than 51. In the meantime, given that 25 members is already enough to reach the maximum expected performance, this section supports the previous conclusion that – to our best knowledge – a 25-member reforecast is fit for verification purposes.

Figure 6: Influence of ensemble size on verification metrics at lead time 1-month for November initialization: CORR (right) and ROCA HT (left), for EU-averaged T2M (top) and NAO (bottom). The verification metrics for each ensemble size are indicated with the means, interquartile range and 95% confidence interval from 1,000 random draws out of 51 members.

Variable	Box (if any)	Verification metric (initialization)	Absolute difference Mean 45 – Mean 25	Min. ensemble size for confidence interval < 0.1
T2M	EU	CORR (Nov)	0.006	40
RR	EU	CORR (Nov)	0.003	45
NAO		CORR (Nov)	0.013	NA
EA		CORR (Nov)	0.010	45
SCAN		CORR (Nov)	0.024	45

Table 5: Summary of key features in the evolution of correlation with ensemble size, at lead time 1-month for November initialization: the absolute difference between the mean of 1,000 random draws of 45 members and 25 members, the minimum ensemble size to reach a confidence interval width less than 0.1 (NA if the width is always greater than 0.1).

Variable	Box (if any)	Verification metric (initialization)	Absolute difference Mean 45 – Mean 25	Min. ensemble size for confidence interval < 0.05
T2M	EU	ROCA HT (Nov)	0.012	40
RR	EU	ROCA HT (Nov)	0.009	20
NAO		ROCA HT (Nov)	0.013	NA
EA		ROCA HT (Nov)	0.012	NA
SCAN		ROCA HT (Nov)	0.019	NA

Table 6: Same as Table 5 for ROCA HT. The threshold for minimum ensemble size is for a confidence interval width less than 0.05 (NA if the width is always greater than 0.05).

7. What is the impact of an alternative forecasting strategy?

The previous sections have shown that, for verification, a 25-member reforecast is roughly as good as a 51-member reforecast. However, a consistent ensemble size between reforecast and real-time bears a scientific interest when evaluating alternative forecasting strategies. This section provides an example where the 51-member reforecast is a necessary benchmark for comparison. In a real-time forecasting context, the baseline strategy is to compute 51 members at every month M. Instead, we might take advantage of the previous initialization (M-1) that also covers the target season with a 1-month shift. The alternative strategy ensuring an ensemble size similar to 51 members is to combine 25 members issued at month M (LT1) and 25 members issued at month M-1 (LT2).

Figure 7: Comparison of several verification metrics for the target seasons, according to two forecasting strategies: 51 members initialized 1 month before (orange) vs 25 members initialized 1 month before + 25 members initialized 2 months before (blue).

Figure 7 illustrates the comparison between the baseline strategy, verified thanks to the extended reforecast, and this alternative strategy. The verification metrics are the same as in Figure 3 while in that case, the error bars are the 95% confidence interval of a bootstrap procedure with replacement (i.e 1,000 random draws of 51 members out of 51). The overall conclusion from Figure 7 is that combining two sets of 25 members initialized one month apart leads to forecast performances that are close to those of 51 members initialized the same month for the forecast range months 1-3. Yet, there are some notable exceptions such as NAO correlation in MAM (where the baseline strategy is far better) and in DJF (where the alternative strategy outperforms the baseline). Although we will not recommend to decrease the real-time ensemble size and switch to a combination of consecutive 25-member fore-

casts, this result indicates that introducing forecast members from the previous month in the current real-time forecast might be worthwhile to increase the ensemble size.

8. Conclusion and recommendation

This deliverable has shown that a 25-member reforecast for the Météo-France seasonal forecasting system is sufficient for most applications such as sampling the model climatology, bias correction and forecast verification. Regarding verification, the official 25-member reforecast does not exhibit strong discrepancies with the extended 51-member reforecast considered as the benchmark: the various scores remain close in terms of numerical values, exhibit the same variations with season and lead time, and are similarly influenced by the climate change trend. Admittedly, because 25 members represent an undersampling of the real-time ensemble size, there is uncertainty on the numerical values for some verification metrics, that might not be fully robust to a change in perturbations generating the members. Nonetheless, there is no indication from the present reforecast extension protocol that 51 members are any more sufficient to provide a robust estimate of the intrinsic performances of the forecasting system.

The above conclusions do not encourage us to suggest the increase of reforecast ensemble size as a priority for the next seasonal forecasting system, especially if computational resources are limited. However, those conclusions intervene within a “traditional” use of reforecasts, i.e for skill assessment and forecast evaluation purposes. In the meantime, having the same number of members in reforecasts and real-time forecasts provides consistency that may serve other science purposes, such as evaluating alternative forecasting strategies. For all these reasons, we recommend the extension of reforecast ensemble size in the next Météo-France seasonal forecasting system provided it can be done without leading us to discard possible improvements to the coupled model which require similar computational resources.

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10. Appendix

Figure A1: Same as Figure 3 (CORR and ROCA HT at lead time 1-month for the February, May, August and November initializations) for the additional parameters mentioned in Tables 1 and 2: INDO-averaged T2M, INDO-averaged RR, BRNE-averaged T2M, BRNE-averaged RR and East Atlantic (EA) mode.

Figure A2: Same as Figure 4 (CORR and ROCA HT at lead time 0 to 4-month in the November initialization) for the additional parameters mentioned in Tables 3 and 4: INDO-averaged T2M, INDO-averaged RR, BRNE-averaged T2M, BRNE-averaged RR and East Atlantic (EA) mode.

Figure A3: Same as Figure 6 (influence of ensemble size on CORR and ROCA HT at lead time 1-month for the November initialization) for the additional parameters mentioned in Tables 5 and 6: EU-averaged RR, East Atlantic (EA) and Scandinavian Blocking (SCAN) mode.

